

Coupling Effect on Axial Compressive Buckling of Laminated Composite Cylindrical Shells

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ABSTRACT

In general, laminated composite structures exhibit the coupling effect due to the anisotropy and the unsymmetric lamination. Thus, for a small number of layers, they behave quite differently from the homogeneous orthotropic ones.

In the present paper, such coupling effects on the buckling stresses in the cross-ply and angle-ply laminated cylindrical shells under axial compression are discussed. They are analysed by use of the Donnell-type equilibrium equations or of the approximate energy method under two kinds of boundary conditions for simply-supported edges, by considering two kinds of buckling modes. The analytical predictions on the effects of stacking sequence, number of laminae and dimensions of cylindrical shells etc. were verified by carrying out the buckling experiments on carbon-fiber/epoxy (CFRP) laminated cylinders. The experiments showed a good agreement with the analytical results.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced fiber-reinforced composite materials have been used for structural members in aeronautical and astronautical fields, because of their high specific strength and stiffness. Such laminated composite shells behave differently from homogeneous orthotropic shells due to the coupling effect, except for the case of symmetric cross-ply laminates (1), (2).

Experimental and analytical investigations on buckling of filament-wound or laminated cylindrical shells under axial compression have been done by Tasi(3), (4), Card(5), Khot(6) and Hirano(7) etc. However, they assumed the shells as homogeneous ones without discussing the coupling effect on buckling stress. Jones (8) analysed the coupling effect only for the cross-ply laminated cylinders.

In the present paper, the coupling effect on the axial buckling stresses of the cross-ply and angle-ply laminated cylinders simply-supported at both edges are analysed. Then, the analytical predictions are compared with the test results on CFRP cylinders with a variety of lamination angles and constitutions.

2. FUNDAMENTAL EQUATIONS FOR LAMINATED CYLINDRICAL SHELLS UNDER AXIAL COMPRESSION

The cylindrical coordinate system (x, y, z) is used as shown in Fig.1.

2.1 Relations between Strain and Displacement Components

The axial, circumferential and shear strains at any point within the shell thickness based on the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis are

$$\epsilon_x = \epsilon_x^0 + z\kappa_x, \quad \epsilon_y = \epsilon_y^0 + z\kappa_y, \quad \gamma_{xy} = \gamma_{xy}^0 + z\kappa_{xy} \quad (1)$$

where $\epsilon_x^0, \epsilon_y^0, \gamma_{xy}^0$; normal and shearing strains on the middle surface
 $\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}$; bending and torsional changes in curvature
 are expressed as follows for a circular cylindrical shell of radius R.

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x^0 &= u, x & \epsilon_y^0 &= v, y + w/R & \gamma_{xy}^0 &= v, x + u, y \\ \kappa_x &= -w, xx & \kappa_y &= -w, yy & \kappa_{xy} &= -2w, xy \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where u, v, w; additional displacement components due to buckling in the x-, y- and z-directions, respectively, on the middle surface.

Fig.1. Configuration and coordinate of cylindrical shell.

2.2 Constitutive Equations

The constitutive equations of the force and moment resultants versus the strains and changes in curvature on the middle surface are described as

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ \hline B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_x^0 \\ \epsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Fig.2. Geometry of an N-layered laminate

The in-plane, coupling and bending stiffness matrices A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} are defined by use of the transformed reduced stiffnesses, \bar{Q}_{ij} ($i, j=1, 2, 6$) as follows.

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)} [(t_{k+1} - t_k), (t_{k+1}^2 - t_k^2)/2, (t_{k+1}^3 - t_k^3)/3] \quad (4)$$

where the index "k" denotes the 'k'th layer (see Fig.2).

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Q}_{11} &= Q_{11}\alpha^4 + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\alpha^2\beta^2 + Q_{22}\beta^4, & \bar{Q}_{12} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66})\alpha^2\beta^2 + Q_{12}(\alpha^4 + \beta^4) \\ \bar{Q}_{22} &= Q_{11}\beta^4 + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\alpha^2\beta^2 + Q_{22}\alpha^4, & \bar{Q}_{66} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\alpha^2\beta^2 + Q_{66}(\alpha^4 + \beta^4) \\ \bar{Q}_{16} &= -(Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\alpha^3\beta + (Q_{22} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\alpha\beta^3 \\ \bar{Q}_{26} &= -(Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\alpha\beta^3 + (Q_{22} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\alpha^3\beta \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \cos \theta_k, \quad \beta = \sin \theta_k, \quad \theta_k; \text{ lamination angle in the 'k'th lamina} \\ Q_{11} &= E_L / (1 - \nu_L \nu_T), \quad Q_{22} = \nu_T E_L / (1 - \nu_L \nu_T), \quad Q_{12} = E_T / (1 - \nu_L \nu_T), \quad Q_{66} = G_{LT} \\ E_L, E_T, \nu_L, \nu_T, G_{LT}; & \text{ material constants of unidirectional composites} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2.3. Governing Equilibrium Equations

The Donnell-type equilibrium equations in the x-, y- and z-directions can be derived in terms of displacement components as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11}u, xx + A_{12}(v, xy + w, x/R) + A_{16}(v, xx + u, xy) - B_{11}w, xxx - B_{12}w, xyy - 2B_{16}w, xxy \\ + A_{16}u, xy + A_{26}(v, yy + w, y/R) + A_{66}(v, xy + u, yy) - B_{16}w, xxy - B_{26}w, yyy - 2B_{66}w, xyy = 0 \\ A_{16}u, xx + A_{26}(v, xy + w, x/R) + A_{66}(v, xx + u, xy) - B_{16}w, xxx - B_{26}w, xyy - 2B_{66}w, xxy \\ + A_{12}u, xy + A_{22}(v, yy + w, y/R) + A_{26}(v, xy + u, yy) - B_{12}w, xxy - B_{22}w, yyy - 2B_{26}w, xyy = 0 \\ B_{11}u, xxx + B_{12}(v, xxy + w, xx/R) + B_{16}(v, xxx + u, xxy) - D_{11}w, xxx - D_{12}w, xxy \\ - 2D_{16}w, xxy + 2[B_{16}u, xxy + B_{26}(v, xxy + w, xy/R) + B_{66}(v, xxy + u, xyy) - D_{16}w, xxy \\ - D_{26}w, xyy - 2D_{66}w, xyy] + B_{12}u, xyy + B_{22}(v, yyy + w, yy/R) + B_{26}(v, xyy + u, yyy) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -D_{12} w_{,xyxy} - D_{22} w_{,yyyy} - 2D_{26} w_{,xyyy} - [A_{12} u_{,x} + A_{22} (v_{,y} + w/R) + A_{26} (v_{,x} + u_{,y}) \\
 & - B_{12} w_{,xx} - B_{22} w_{,yy} - 2B_{26} w_{,xy}] / R + \bar{N}_x w_{,xx} = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

where \bar{N}_x is the in-plane axial force applied in the x-direction.

2.4. Total Potential Energy

The total potential energy used for an approximate energy method is given by

$$\Pi_p = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^{2\pi R} [N_x \epsilon_x^0 + N_y \epsilon_y^0 + N_{xy} \gamma_{xy}^0 + M_x \kappa_x + M_y \kappa_y + M_{xy} \kappa_{xy} - \bar{N}_x (w_{,x})^2] dx dy \quad (8)$$

2.5 Boundary Conditions

The following two boundary conditions for the simply-supported edges are used.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (S-2) \text{ condition ; } w = M_x = v = N_x = 0 \text{ at } x=0, L \\
 & (S-3) \text{ condition ; } w = M_x = u = N_{xy} = 0 \text{ at } x=0, L
 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

3. ANALYTICAL SOLUTIONS AND NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

3.1 Fundamental Mechanical Properties of Unidirectional CFRP

The fundamental elastic constants of unidirectional carbon-fiber/epoxy composites with fiber volume content $V_f=60\%$ used for the numerical calculations are $E_L=137$ GPa (13940 kgf/mm²), $E_T=8.17$ GPa (833 kgf/mm²), $\nu_L=0.316$, $\nu_T=0.0189$, $G_{LT}=4.75$ GPa (484 kgf/mm²).

These values can be estimated by explicit algebraic formulae when the constituent materials and V_f are specified. They were verified by experiments (9).

3.2 Buckling Stresses Obtained by Equilibrium Equations for Cross-ply Laminated Cylindrical Shells

For the cross-ply laminates consisting of the 0° and 90° laminae, $A_{16}=A_{26}=0$ and $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$. There is no coupling between bending and extension in symmetric laminates, but the coupling terms $B_{11}=-B_{22}$ only appear in antisymmetric laminates. This comes from the difference of locations of the middle and neutral surfaces.

(1) Analytical Formulae for Buckling Stresses

In the case where the unsymmetric buckling modes occur, the following displacement components which satisfy the (S-2) boundary condition are used.

$$u = u_{mn} \cos(m\pi x/L) \sin(ny/R), v = v_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/L) \cos(ny/R), w = w_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/L) \sin(ny/R) \quad (10)$$

where m is number of half waves in buckle pattern in the axial direction, n is number of full waves in the circumferential direction, L is length of cylinder and u_{mn} , v_{mn} and w_{mn} are amplitudes of displacement components.

The buckling stress corresponding to the specified wave numbers m and n , can be obtained as eigenvalue by substituting Eqs.(10) into Eqs.(7).

$$\bar{N}_x = -\bar{\sigma}_t = (L/m\pi)^2 [T_{33} + (2T_{12}T_{13}T_{23} - T_{11}T_{23}^2 - T_{22}T_{13}^2) / (T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2)] \quad (11)$$

where, in both symmetric and antisymmetric laminates:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & T_{11} = A_{11}(m\pi/L)^2 + A_{66}(n/R)^2, \quad T_{12} = (A_{12} + A_{66})(m\pi/L)(n/R), \quad T_{22} = A_{22}(n/R)^2 + A_{66}(m\pi/L)^2 \\
 & \text{in symmetric laminates:} \\
 & T_{13} = -A_{12}(m\pi/L)/R, \quad T_{23} = -A_{22}(n/R)/R, \\
 & T_{33} = D_{11}(m\pi/L)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})(m\pi/L)^2(n/R)^2 + D_{22}(n/R)^4 + A_{22}/R^2
 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

in antisymmetric laminates:

$$T_{13} = -[A_{12}(m\pi/L)/R + B_{11}(m\pi/L)^3], \quad T_{23} = -[A_{22}(n/R)/R - B_{11}(n/R)^3],$$

$$T_{33} = D_{11}(m\pi/L)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})(m\pi/L)^2(n/R)^2 + D_{22}(n/R)^4 + A_{22}/R^2 - 2B_{11}(n/R)^2/R$$

The lowest buckling stresses are searched numerically for various possible values of integers m and n under a particular set of shell curvature parameter $Z=L^2/Rt$ and the radius-to-thickness ratio R/t .

In the case of axisymmetric buckling mode, the buckling stresses can be obtained easily by putting $n=0$ in the above formulae (11) and (12).

(2) Numerical Results and Discussions

The buckling stresses with unsymmetric buckling modes are much lower than those with axisymmetric ones. Accordingly, only the buckling stresses with

Fig.3 Variation of buckling coefficients of cross-ply cylinders with a parameter Z

unsymmetric modes of symmetric and antisymmetric cross-ply shells are shown in the form of nondimensional coefficients $K = \sigma_x R / E_T t$ in Fig.3(a) and (b), respectively. The K-values are almost constant independently of the shape parameter $Z = L/Rt$ in the range of $Z > 100$, but increase with decrease of Z in the range of small Z which means the approach of shell buckling to plate buckling.

The effect of number of layers, N, on the K-values is small for the symmetric laminated shell; however, for the antisymmetric laminated shell, the K-values are considerably decreased for small number of layers because of the coupling effect. The coupling effect between bending and extension rapidly dies out as the number of layers increases. The K-values for an infinite number of layers are the same with those of orthotropic homogeneous shells. Whether the inner layer is either 0° - or 90° - one has little effect on the K-values in the range of $Z > 10$.

3.3 Buckling Stresses Obtained by Approximate Energy Method for Angle-ply Laminated Cylindrical Shells

For the angle-ply laminates consisting of $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ laminae, the extension-twisting (shear-bending) coupling stiffnesses B_{16} , B_{26} appear in the antisymmetric angle-ply laminates, while the extension-shear coupling stiffnesses A_{16} , A_{26} and the bending-twisting coupling stiffnesses D_{16} , D_{26} appear in the symmetric angle-ply laminates. The presence of these terms in the governing equations and boundary conditions make a closed-form solution impossible. Accordingly, the Ritz method based on the principle of stationary potential energy are used to obtain the approximate buckling stresses.

(1) Analytical Formulae for Buckling Stresses

① In the case where the unsymmetric buckling modes occur, the following displacement components are used.

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Under (S-2) condition;} \\ &u = u_{mn} \cos(m\pi x/L) \sin(ny/R), v = v_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/L) \cos(ny/R), w = w_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/L) \sin(ny/R) \\ &\text{Under (S-3) condition;} \\ &u = u_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/L) \cos(ny/R), v = v_{mn} \cos(m\pi x/L) \sin(ny/R), w = w_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/L) \sin(ny/R) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The potential energy Π_p obtained by substituting Eqs.(2) and (13) into Eq.(8) are minimized with respect to the displacement amplitudes, that is,

$$\Pi_p, u_{mn} = \Pi_p, v_{mn} = \Pi_p, w_{mn} = 0 \quad (14)$$

which give the buckling stresses in the same form as Eq.(11). The constant T_{1j} ($i, j=1, 2, 3$) used in Eq.(11) are the same as Eq.(12) under the (S-2) condition; however, under the (S-3) condition, the constants T_{13} and T_{23} are given by Eqs. (15) even though the constants T_{11} , T_{12} , T_{22} and T_{33} are the same as Eqs.(12).

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{In symmetric laminates;} \quad T_{13} = -A_{26}(n/R)/R, \quad T_{23} = -A_{26}(m\pi/L)/R \\ &\text{In antisymmetric laminates;} \quad T_{13} = -[3B_{16}(m\pi/L)^2 + B_{26}(n/R)^2] / (n/R) \\ &\quad \quad \quad T_{23} = -[B_{16}(m\pi/L)^2 + 3B_{26}(n/R)^2] / (m\pi/L) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

② In the case where the axisymmetric buckling modes occur, the buckling stresses are given in the following simplified equations.

Fig. 4 Variations of buckling coefficients in angle-ply cylinders under (S-2) condition.

(a) Symmetric laminate (b) Antisymmetric laminate
Fig. 5 Variations of buckling coefficients in angle-ply cylinders with unsymmetric buckling modes under (S-3) condition.

Under (S-2) condition; $\bar{N}_x = \bar{\sigma}_x t = (L/m\pi)^2 [A_{22}/R^2 - A_{12}^2/A_{11}R^2 + D_{11}(m\pi/L)^4]$

Under (S-3) condition;
In symmetric laminates $:\bar{N}_x = (L/m\pi)^2 [A_{22}/R^2 - A_{26}^2/A_{66}R^2 + D_{11}(m\pi/L)^4]$ (16)

In antisymmetric laminates: $\bar{N}_x = (L/m\pi)^2 [A_{22}/R^2 - (B_{16}^2/A_{66})(m\pi/L)^4 + D_{11}(m\pi/L)^4]$

(2) Numerical Results and Discussions

The lowest buckling stresses are searched for various possible values of integers m and n. The nondimensional buckling stresses, that is, K-values which are almost constant independently of the shape parameter Z in the range of $Z \geq 100$ are plotted in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 for the cases under the (S-2) and (S-3) boundary conditions, respectively.

As for the effect of buckling modes, under the (S-2) condition as shown in Fig. 4, the unsymmetric modes give almost the same buckling stresses with the axisymmetric ones in the range of $20^\circ < \theta < 70^\circ$, but give the lower buckling stresses in the ranges of $\theta < 20^\circ$ and $\theta > 70^\circ$ with a large number of n. It is a contrary to the previous results obtained by others(7). However, under the (S-3) condition, the unsymmetric modes give almost the same buckling stresses with the axisymmetric ones in both symmetric and antisymmetric laminates. Hence, only the K-values with the unsymmetric modes are shown in Fig. 5.

As for the effect of lamination angle, θ , the buckling stresses are minimum at $\theta = 45^\circ$ in the range of $20^\circ < \theta < 70^\circ$ under the (S-2) condition, but are maximum by contraries under the (S-3) condition in the case of $N \geq 4$; However, in the special case of $N=2$ in the antisymmetric laminate, the buckling stresses are minimum at $\theta = 20^\circ$ under the (S-3) condition.

As for the effect of number of layers, N, the coupling effect of laminates rapidly dies out as N increases, and the buckling stresses become close to those for homogeneous orthotropic laminated shells; However, it should be noted that the buckling stresses are much decreased when N is extremely small in antisymmetric laminates because of the influence of the extension-twisting coupling stiffnesses B_{16} , B_{26} under the (S-3) condition.

As for the effect of stacking sequence, both symmetric and antisymmetric laminations give almost the same buckling stresses with an increase of N except the case of $N=2$ with antisymmetric lamination as mentioned above.

4. EXPERIMENTS OF CFRP LAMINATED CYLINDRICAL SHELLS UNDER AXIAL COMPRESSION

In order to verify the analytical results as mentioned above, the buckling experiments of CFRP laminated shells were carried out under axial compression.

Table 1. Comparison of analytical and experimental buckling stresses

type of lamination	lami-nate constitution S:sym. A:anti.	lami-nate angle θ ($^{\circ}$)	number of layers N	thick-ness t (mm)	specimen notation	analytical buckling stress (kgf/mm ²)				experimen-tal buckling stress (kgf/mm ²)	analy-tical comp. fracture stress (kgf/mm ²)
						boundary cond. (S-2)		boundary cond. (S-3)			
						axisym. mode	unsym. mode	axisym. mode	unsym. mode		
cross-ply(C)	S	0+90	8	1	CS-0+90-8-1	46.3	16.0			13.7,13.4	
	A	0+90	2	1	CA-0+90-2-1	24.5	10.9			10.5,10.7	
angle-ply(A)	A	20	2	0.5	AA- 20 -2-1	9.11	9.13	7.14	7.15	3.95	69.3
	A		1	1	AA- 20 -2-1	18.2	18.3	14.3	14.3	9.23,8.98	
	A		8	1	AA- 20 -8-1	18.2	18.3	19.9	20.3	13.4	
	S	45	4	0.5	AS- 45-4-0.5	7.88	7.93	12.5	12.6	4.30	
	A		2	0.5	AA- 45-2-0.5	7.88	7.93	8.62	8.64	4.30	
	A		1	1	AA- 45-2-1	15.8	16.0	17.3	17.3	7.96	
	A	8	1	AA- 45-8-1	15.8	16.0	24.6	24.8	9.23,9.23		
	S	70	8	1	AS- 70-8-1	18.2	18.3	20.3	20.4	12.9,12.1	
	A		4	0.5	AA- 70-4-0.5	9.10	9.12	9.96	9.98	6.05	
	A		2	1	AA- 70-2-1	18.2	18.3	18.8	18.9	9.55,9.55	
	A	8	1	AA- 70-8-1	18.2	18.3	20.2	20.3	13.1,12.7		

4.1 Specimens and Experimental Procedures

The test specimens as shown in Table 1. were manufactured by wrapping the carbon-fiber/epoxy unidirectional prepreg sheets. The dimensions of cylinders are 0.5mm (4 laminae) or 1mm (8 laminae) in thickness, and 300mm or 600mm in length. The radius-to-thickness ratio is 200 or 100. A variety of laminate configurations, that is, thirteen kinds of laminated cylindrical shells with four kinds of lamination angles, θ , such as $0^{\circ}+90^{\circ}$, $\pm 20^{\circ}$, $\pm 45^{\circ}$ and $\pm 70^{\circ}$ were used. The notation of specimens is explained as below, with an example.

The cylinder was positioned on the lower table of testing machine so that the compression might act on the center of cylinder. A hemispherical cup was placed on the top end plate in order to avoid the bending moment. This adjustment was ascertained by the axial and circumferential strain gages cemented on the outer and inner surfaces at four points around the mid-center of cylinder. The axial shortening and the lateral displacements on the mid-center of cylinder were measured by using dialgages.

4.2 Comparison of Experimental Results with Analytical Predictions and Discussion

The measured axial shortening, lateral displacement and strains increased proportionally with an increase of axial compression until the shell buckled with a bang and a sudden reduction in load.

(1) In the case of cross-ply cylinders

The 2-tier diamond-shaped patterns were observed in experiments as shown in Fig.6 and as usually seen in isotropic metal shells under axial compression. The unsymmetric buckling modes occurred with lower buckling stresses according to the analytical prediction under the (S-2) boundary condition, which is considered to be more practical in experiments. The buckling stresses obtained are compared with the numerical results in Table 1. and in Fig.3. As predicted in the analysis for antisymmetric cross-ply laminates, the buckling stresses decreased due to the coupling between bending and extension, and the buckling stresses in the case of N=2 were lower than N=8. The experiments showed a good agreement with the analytical predictions.

(2) In the case of angle-ply cylinders

The unsymmetric 2-tier diamond-shaped buckles uniformly distributed around cylinders were observed in $\theta=20^{\circ}$, 45° and 70° specimens as shown in Fig.6. The experimental buckling stresses are compared with the numerical results in Fig.7. The average experimental buckling stresses were found to lie within 50% to 70% of the theoretical values, probably due to the significant sensitivity to various

Fig.6. Post-buckling behaviors of CFRP laminated cylindrical shells under axial compression

kinds of imperfections. The practical boundary condition (S-2) gives the lower buckling stresses than the (S-3) condition except around $\theta=20^\circ$ in the special case of $N=2$ with antisymmetric lamination. The experimental buckling stresses were much decreased in the case of $N=2$ in antisymmetric laminates due to the extension-twisting coupling.

As for the effect of lamination angle, θ , the buckling stresses were lowest at $\theta=45^\circ$, as predicted by analysis under the (S-2) boundary condition except the case of $N=2$ with antisymmetric lamination.

The stacking sequence or the laminate constitution had little effect on the buckling stresses as seen by comparing the experimental results for $\theta=45^\circ$ and $\theta=70^\circ$, as predicted by analysis under the (S-2) boundary condition.

In the angle-ply laminated cylinders having thickness $t=1\text{mm}$ and lamination angle $\theta=45^\circ$ and 70° , the failure occurred suddenly without exhibiting the buckle patterns. It might be probably induced by the material fracture. According to the previous work done by the senior author (10) on the compressive fracture strength of helical-wound cylinders as shown in Table 1, the buckling of cylinders with $t=1\text{mm}$ and $\theta=70^\circ$ seemed to take place almost simultaneously accompanying the compressive fracture.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The coupling effect on buckling of laminated cylinder under compression was analysed and verified by experiments on CFRP laminated cylindrical shells. The principal conclusions can be summarized as follows.

- (1) The nondimensional buckling coefficients of cylindrical shells are almost independent of the shape parameters $Z=L^2/Rt$ and R/t .
- (2) As the number of layers increases, the coupling effect of laminates rapidly dies out and the buckling stresses become close to those for homogeneous orthotropic cylinders. The buckling stresses are much decreased especially when $N=2$

Fig.7. Comparison of experimental buckling stresses with analytical predictions in angle-ply cylinders.

with antisymmetric lamination in both cross-ply and angle-ply cylinders.

(3) In the cross-ply laminated cylindrical shells, the unsymmetric buckling modes give the lower buckling stresses than the axisymmetric ones. While, in the angle-ply laminated cylindrical shells, the unsymmetric buckling modes give similarly the lower buckling stresses only in the range of $\theta < 20^\circ$ and $\theta > 70^\circ$, but give almost the same buckling stresses with the axisymmetric ones in the range of $20^\circ < \theta < 70^\circ$, and the buckling stresses are minimum at $\theta = 45^\circ$ which is contrary to the previous results obtained by others.

(4) As for the effect of the boundary conditions for simply-supported edges, the (S-2) condition which seems to be practical in experiments gives the lower buckling stresses except that the (S-3) condition gives the lower ones around $\theta = 20^\circ$ only in the case of $N=2$ with antisymmetric lamination.

(5) The experimental results on CFRP laminated cylindrical shells agreed fairly with the analytical predictions mentioned above, showing the various effects of stacking sequence, number of layers and dimension of cylinder etc..

The analysis will be more refined in the following paper so as to satisfy the boundary conditions for the laminated cylindrical shells.

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